

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Improving a Time-Stretching Technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation

Davide Busacca

Supervisor: Dr. Xavier Serra

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Dedication

To a friend always smiling,

to a friend always showing his best.

Thank you for the unforgettable parties enjoyed together,
thank you for the delightful pictures jealously stored in my heart.

Until we meet again, Campione.

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Abstract

Transient smearing, transient duplication and transient skipping are well-known artefacts introduced by time-stretching (TS) techniques. Aiming to avoid these artefacts transient preservation extensions are applied to TS techniques. Typically, the transients are detected in time/frequency regions. Then, a transient preservation processing is applied to these regions.

The TS Technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation (HPS) relies on a conceptually easy approach to transient preservation that does not need an explicit transients detection in time. This approach is based on the separation of the input signal into the Harmonic and the Percussive components, where ideally only and exclusively the latter contains transients. A phase vocoder is applied to the harmonic component, whereas an overlap-add with parameters optimized to process transients is applied to the percussive component. The authors of the technique claimed that it preserves effectively transients and they highlighted the simplicity of their approach in comparison to other methods based on explicit transients detection in time.

In this thesis, we describe and criticize the mentioned technique. We then propose to change the HPS method used to compute the components and evaluate the audio quality of the transformations obtained using the two systems.

We found out that the proposed system improves the original on complex harmonic/percussive mixtures. However, the leaking of harmonic elements into the percussive component and the inverse leaking are often cause of not negligible TS artefacts in both systems, such as pitch distortion and transient smearing.

We conclude suggesting that the technique could benefit from the use of a multi-resolutional phase vocoder avoiding the overlap-add. Implementing a scheme for explicit transient detection might be necessary.

Keywords: Time-Stretching; Time-Scale Modification; Overlap-Add; Phase Vocoder; Transient Preservation; Harmonic/Percussive Separation;

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Time-Stretching

Time-Stretching (TS) is the modification of the duration of an audio signal while preserving other audio qualities, such as the the frequential information which arouses the pitch sensation.

TS can be used in a huge range of audio applications. For example, in post-synchronization the soundtrack may have a different length respect to the image it is supposed to accompany. TS can be used to to modify the duration of the audio, hence synchronizing audio and image.

TS can also be defined as the modification of the tempo of a recording. Let us think of DJ who wants to mix two tracks to cover when one finishes and the other one starts. By matching the tempo of the next track to the tempo of the one playing synchronous playback is enabled. In another example, we have a producer who wants to insert a drum loop into his new production, but needs to change the speed of the loop to match the tempo of the recording. Digital Audio Workstations, such as Live from Ableton, allow to modify the tempo with a pair of clicks.

Learning how to play an instrument can be supported by online material, but sometime it is useful to play these resources slower. A newbie guitar player can use TS to slow down recordings to facilitate the understanding of the material or to play on top of it. A similar example is related to acquisition of a new language. Let

us suppose that you are an Italian speaker who is trying to learn Spanish. At the beginning is quite likely that you need to listen to slow speeches in order to understand. Whether you can ask a speaker to talk slower, the Google YouTube platform allows to slow down the speed of the video streaming. However, the application of naive TS cannot reproduce perfectly the behaviour modification of speakers or musicians when they are asked to change the words rate or the played tempo. For example, when humans speak slower they tend to put more emphasis on the vocals than on the consonants, whereas naive TS will process the whole signal equally.

In addition, TS can be used for Pitch Shifting (PS). PS can be thought as the inverse process of TS, in which the pitch of an audio signal is modified without affecting its duration. Samplers are based on this process. A sampler is a synthesizer whose sound is based on an recorded audio signal. This sound is transformed to obtain different pitches. For example, we could create a sampler to emulate the sound of multiple notes played on the piano starting from the recording of only one note. This approach is out-of-date, as today digital samplers can hold innumerable recordings of piano notes. However, refined version of PS are still used today. Let us think about software such as Auto-Tune by Antares or Melodyne from Celemony. These allow to modify the base frequency of singing speech signals to apply pitch-correction or for artistic means.

TS has been used in greater or lesser creative forms in a zillion of musical pieces. We can point out to the central breakdown section of Fatboy Slim's "Rockafeller Skunk" (1998).

The range of application of TS seems really infinite, and the details which can be discussed about each application nonetheless.

However, there is a problem that emerges while using TS. The transformation tends to introduce unwanted artefacts, affecting the audio quality of the modified version. From one side, different approaches introduce different types of artefacts, whereas different final application show different needs. This suggest that a formula which perfectly fit an application might not be suitable for another application. The TS artefacts will be thoroughly treated in the thesis.

1.2 Harmonic/Percussive Separation for Time-Stretching

Harmonic/Percussive Separation (HPS) attempts to separate the pitch instruments from the percussion instruments. This has numerous applications including remixing and DJing. In addition, this can be used as pre-processing tool for other tasks including automatic music transcription, chord estimation, key signature detection and onset detection. The elimination of percussive sources allows improved estimation of the pitched content, while the elimination of the pitched sources allows improved results in applications such as rhythm analysis, beat tracking and the automatic transcription of drum instruments.

In 2014 a technique which exploited HPS for TS has been released [Driedger et al., 2014]. The basic idea of this approach consisted of the independent treating of the components obtained from the separation. This proved to be successful for the quality of the results obtained considering its simplicity.

1.3 The Thesis

In this thesis, the Time-Stretching technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation [Driedger et al., 2014] is analyzed and criticized. An improvement based on the modification of the Harmonic/Percussive Separation method is proposed and an evaluation is carried out. A final discussion proposes suggestions for further improvement.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Time-stretching (TS) techniques can be divided in two main families: time-segment processing and time-frequency processing. Time-segment processing techniques modify directly the time representation of the signal. These are computationally efficient, preserve the original timbre but introduce artefacts for polyphonic signals and have the tendency to duplicate or skip transients. On the other side, time-frequency processing techniques use a two dimensional representation of the signal, where both frequency and time information is considered. This are well-suited to deal with polyphonic and harmonic signals. However, time-frequency processing introduce artefacts derived from the loss of vertical phase coherence of the original signal such as phasiness, transient smearing and shape loss.

In this chapter a review of TS techniques is proposed, followed by an introduction to harmonic/percussive separation (HPS) techniques. Finally the TS technique based on HPS [Driedger et al., 2014] is discussed, and potential improvements are proposed.

The reader interested in more detailed TS reviews is pointed to the review paper [Driedger and Müller, 2016] and the DAFX Book's chapters about Time-Segment Processing and Time-Frequency Processing [Zölzer, 2011]. In addition, a Matlab toolbox with the implementation of some TS techniques was released under GPL license [Driedger and Müller, 2014].

2.1 Time-Segment Processing

Figure 1: The standard OLA procedure for Time-Stretching. (a) The analysis frame $x_m[n]$ is obtained from the input signal. (b) An analysis window $w[n]$ is applied to $x_m[n]$ to obtain the synthesis frame $y_m[n]$. (c) The next analysis frame $x_{m+1}[n]$ is picked at distance of the analysis hop size H_a . (d) The new frame is weighted using the analysis window $w[n]$ and added to the output signal at distance of the synthesis hop size H_s . This is an example of time contraction, as the synthesis hop size is smaller than the analysis hop size. The image has been adapted from [Driedger and Müller, 2016].

In time-segment processing the raw input signal is split into short-time frames. Then, these frames are relocated in time to obtain a time contraction or expansion of the original signal. Fig. 1 illustrates the standard overlap-add procedure. Part of the original signals might be omitted or repeated during the modification. The amount of time expansion or contraction depends on the TSM factor α . This is determined by the ratio between the analysis and synthesis hop sizes:

$$\alpha = \frac{H_s}{H_a} \quad (2.1)$$

If $H_s > H_a$ we have a time expansion, whereas if $H_s < H_a$ we have a time contraction. We consider having a fixed synthesis hop size, whereas the analysis hop size is obtained from the time stretching factor and the synthesis hop size:

$$H_a = \frac{H_s}{\alpha} \quad (2.2)$$

2.1.1 Advantages and Disadvantages

Computationally Efficient Time-segment processing is considered computationally efficient as it modifies directly the time-domain representation of the raw waveform. On the other side, time-frequency processing requires the computation of a Short-Time Fourier Transform, which is a computationally expensive operation.

Preserves Timbre The timbre is not affected because the frequency content of the frames is left unmodified. The frames are just relocated in time. On the other side, time-frequency processing modifies the frequency content of the frames and extensions are needed to guarantee timbral characteristics preservation.

Preserves (up to) a single periodicity Extension to the standard overlap-add approach can be used to preserve a periodicity. However, no more than one can be followed. On the other side, time-frequency processing allows to preserve all the periodicities.

2.1.2 Artefacts

Amplitude Discontinuities If two consecutive frames are not aligned in a way that there is a smooth continuation from the end of the previous to the start of the next we encounter amplitude discontinuities. This artefact is heard as a clicking or popping. Windowing is used to solve this problem by tapering to zero at the edge of the analysis frames.

Phase Discontinuities If two consecutive frames are not aligned in a way in which there is a smooth continuation of the phase of each stationary element we en-

counter phase discontinuities. The only way to avoid phase discontinuities is making sure that every frames contain an integer number of cycles for every periodicities in the waveform. However, only up to one pitch can be followed correctly. This suggest that this technique is not suitable for polyphonic signals.

Pitch Distortion Instance of phase discontinuity in which the analysis and/or the synthesis hop sizes have dimension comparable to the periodicity of the waveform. The pitch perceived is affected by these sizes. This artefact is avoided by making sure that the analysis and the synthesis hop sizes are sufficiently greater than the length of a pitch period of the waveform.

Transient Duplication (Presence of Echoes, Stuttering Effect) In time expansion, portions of the signal are relocated farther respect to their original position. Some portions might be repeated in the time-stretched version. The repetition of a transient is perceived as an echoed transient. To avoid this artefact, the TS factor is forced to be one when a transient is detected. However, the application of adaptive dynamic TS ratios to preserve might cause rhythm irregularities.

Transient Skipping (Disappearing of Transients) Transient skipping is the inverse artefact of the transient duplication. In time contraction, portions of the signal are relocated closer respect to their original position. Some portions might be skipped. Transients might be skipped in the time-stretched version. The same solution applied to the transient duplication artefact is effective on transient skipping.

2.2 Time-Frequency Processing

Time-domain processing is able to preserve only up to one periodicity of the input signal. On the other hand, time-frequency processing allows to preserve all the periodicities exploiting a two dimensional representation of the signal using the phase vocoder (PV).

The first channel vocoder was based on the magnitude-only spectrogram [Dudley, 1939].

The PV is instead based on magnitude and phase spectrograms obtained using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) [Flanagan and Golden, 1966]. The PV is named after the exploitation of the phase information of two consecutive frames to refine the rough frequency estimation obtained from the STFT bin index. The computational complexity involved in the PV was significantly reduced by an implementation based on the Fast Fourier Transform [Portnoff, 1976]. The PV was further improved by the substitution of the original phase derivative method used to compute the instantaneous frequency with the phase difference method [Moorer, 1978]. The transformation applied by the PV is made of three steps: analysis, modification and synthesis.

Analysis The analysis STFT provides a time-frequency representation of the input signal in which the one-dimensional input signal $x[n]$ is represented by the complex-valued points $X[m, k]$ in the analysis STFT. This done by the framing of the original signal. Then, each frame is windowed and analyzed with a Discrete Fourier Transform. The complex-valued STFT obtained can be decomposed in the magnitude $|X[m, k]|$ and phase $\angle X[m, k]$ components.

Modification Two modifications are applied to the analysis STFT to obtain the synthesis STFT. First, the analysis hop size and synthesis hop size have different dimensions. This leads to a time relocation of the time position of the synthesis frames. Second, the phases of the synthesis frames are modified to preserve the periodicities of the input signal using the phase propagation equations. The periodic components overlap coherently between synthesis frames avoiding phase jumps. Notice that the magnitude information of each frame is left unchanged by the modification.

Synthesis The output signal is obtained by the application of the inverse-STFT on the synthesis STFT to get its time-domain equivalent. Initially, an inverse discrete Fourier transform is applied to each spectra to obtain the equivalent time-domain frame. Then, these frames are windowed and sum using an overlap-add algorithm. We need to pay attention to not apply an amplitude modulation with the windowing, and we need to consider that the inverse-STFT of a modified STFT usually

does not result in a signal whose STFT is the starting modified STFT. A solution consist in approximate the wanted signal using the Least Squared Error Estimation [Griffin and Lim, 1984].

Phase Coherence The phase propagation applied by the PV guarantees the horizontal phase coherence. This means that each sinusoidal component is free of phase discontinuities between synthesis frames. However, the relations across bins in the frequency direction are lost in this process, giving rise to the “loss of vertical phase coherence”, which is the main cause of the PV artefacts.

2.2.1 Artefacts

Transient Smearing (Transient Vertical Phase Coherence) The loss of vertical phase coherence tends to smear the transients. The phase updating in the phase vocoder assumes that the input sound can be represented as a sum of slowly varying sinusoids. This is not the case for frames showing an abrupt increase in energy, typical of transients. As the phase relationships across the frequency bins representing the transient are lost, the concentrated energy of the transient in the analysis frame gets evenly smeared inside the synthesis frame. The impulsive nature of the transient is lost. This is shown in Fig. 2.

Furthermore, because a single transient is represented in several consecutive analysis frames, the transient energy also get smeared across several synthesis frames. In the case of time expansion the synthesis frames are relocated farther than the analysis frames, resulting in a further spreading of the transient’s energy in time.

The vertical phase coherence at transients can be preserved with the application of a phase reset on transient locations. For instance, when a transient is detected the phases of the bins in the analysis STFT can be directly used in the synthesis STFT [Quatieri et al., 1995]. In a different implementation of the PV, the TS is obtained by reusing or omitting analysis frames in the synthesis STFT [Bonada, 2000]. In this method the TS factor changes locally, as not all the analysis frames are reused or omitted. The vertical phase coherence is preserved by forcing the TS factor to be one on transient locations. However, the factor need to be compensated in the steady

Figure 2: Transient smearing due to loss of vertical phase coherence in phase vocoder. (a) An analysis frame containing a transient. (b) The corresponding synthesis frame which has the same magnitude spectrum as the analysis frame, but a different phase spectrum due to phase modifications. The figure has been adapted from [Damskäg, 2018].

state of the signal around the transient, such that the average TS factor corresponds to the desired amount. The transient detection used by this method can distinguish between transients affecting only the energy in high frequencies, in low frequencies or in the whole band. According to the type of transient detected, a phase reset is applied to the bins in the region of influence of the transient, while standard phase modifications are applied to the remaining bins. However, the adaptive time-varying approach has a pair of inner drawbacks. Irregularities in the rhythm can be added and the compensation might not be transparent for a burst of transients.

Another approach detects and preserves transients at the level of spectral peaks [Röbel, 2003]. Transients are detected when the analysis window slides over them using the center of gravity (COG). Fig. 3 shows the COG of the short-time signal as the analysis window slides over a transient. The COG is computed considering a subset of the STFT frequency bins. A statistical model is used to distinguish between positive COG values introduced by transients, from ones introduced by amplitude modulated sinusoids or noise. Transients detected at the level of spectral peaks are further grouped on a sub-band level. When a transient onset is detected on a sub-band, the spectral peaks whose COG values are above a threshold are collected into a non-contracting set of transient bins, until the end of the transient event. In order to prevent transient smearing, during synthesis, the magnitude and

instantaneous frequencies of the previous frame are used for the transient bins. The end of the transient event is detected when the analysis window is centered on the transient. When the end is detected the phases of the transient bins are reset.

Figure 3: Center of Gravity depending on the time position of the transient in the frame. (a) When the transient is on the right edge the COG is positive. (b) When the transient is on the center and the COG approaches zero. (c) When the transient is on the left edge the COG is negative. The figure has been adapted from [Damskäg, 2018].

Phasiness (Intra-Sinusoidal Vertical Phase Coherence) The loss of vertical phase coherence affects the amplitude envelope of each sinusoidal component. The loss of vertical phase coherence on a constant-amplitude sinusoidal chirp signal leads to fluctuation in the amplitude of the time-stretched version, as shown in Fig. 4. Actually, the amplitude of a sinusoid depends on the phase relationship of the STFT bins representing the sinusoid.

After windowing the energy of each sinusoidal component is shared between more than one bin. The number of bins depends on the type of window applied and whether the sinusoid is perfectly tuned to a bin frequency. Any error in the estimation of the instantaneous frequencies leads to a modification of the phase relations between the bins representing the sinusoid in the analysis STFT and in the synthesis STFT. Considering the iterative fashion in which the PV is applied, once that the phase relations are lost, they will not align in any future frames neither.

Phase locking schemes has been proposed to solve this issue. In loose phase locking the standard phase vocoder processing is applied on all the bins. Then, a phase correction step is applied, such that the phase of neighboring bins affects each other [Puckette, 1995]. Rigid phase locking schemes are instead based on finding

Figure 4: Loss of vertical phase coherence artefact on a chirp. (a) Amplitude of a constant-amplitude chirp. (b) The amplitude of the constant-amplitude chirp after the phase vocoder with factor $\alpha = 1.6$. The figure has been adapted from [Laroche and Dolson, 1999].

peaks in the spectrum, and process the bins related to each peak in a joint fashion [Laroche and Dolson, 1997] [Laroche and Dolson, 1999]. In the identity phase locking scheme a peak is a bin whose amplitude is larger than its four closest bins in frequency direction. The bins surrounding a peak are attached to its “region of influence”. The standard phase propagation is applied only to the peak bins. Then, the synthesis STFT phases of the bins in each region of influence are updated preserving the same phase difference these bins have with the relative peak bin in the analysis STFT. The scaled phase locking scheme is an extension of the identity one, in which peak trajectories are formed to track sinusoids moving between peak bins in consecutive frames. The phase propagation of the peak bins is applied starting from the phase of the previous frame peak bin in the region of influence instead of being always chained to the previous phase of the current peak bin.

Timbre Distortion (Inter-Sinusoidal Vertical Phase Coherence) The phase coherence between the partials of a harmonic signal can be lost similarly to what happens to the phase coherence of the bins representing a sinusoid. The loss of the inter-sinusoidal phase coherence changes the waveform of the processed harmonic

signal. Fig. 5 shows the shape loss on a sawtooth waveform. Whereas the loss of the shape of the time domain waveform is uncritical for most signals, it is clearly audible for speech, because the perception of the underlying excitation pulses is affected.

Figure 5: Shape loss artefact on a sawtooth. (a) The input sawtooth waveform. (b) The sawtooth modified with identity phase-locked vocoder [Laroche and Dolson, 1999]. The shape of the two waveforms clearly differ. The figure has been adapted from [Damskågg, 2018].

Stereo Image The phase and amplitude relations between left and right channels need to be preserved in order to keep the stereo image. As the magnitude is not modified by the PV, it is enough to ensure that the left and right channels frames have the same time tag. Only the phase relations between the two channels need to be carefully locked. This can be done by maintaining the phase difference between the spectral peaks of the analysis STFT of the two channels in the synthesis STFT [Bonada, 2000].

2.2.2 Other approaches

Time-Stretching using the Sinusoidal Modeling In sinusoidal modeling a sum of time-varying sinusoids is used to explicitly model the time-frequency representation of the input signal [McAulay and Quatieri, 1986]. For each short-time spectra, the most dominant peaks are estimated. Each peak is parametrized with the amplitudes, frequencies and phases of the sinusoids modeled. Sinusoidal peak continuation is obtained by forming trajectories between sinusoidal peaks in consecutive frames. The modeled signal is obtained by additive synthesis of the estimated sinusoids.

The sinusoidal model was extended with the sinusoids and noise model. The part of the signal which is not modeled by the time-varying sinusoids defined as residual

is modeled as noise [Serra and Smith, 1990]. The residual is obtained from the subtraction of the signal obtained using the sinusoidal model from the original signal. This is done frame wise, obtaining a series of short-time spectra representing the noise component. The noise spectra are modeled using an estimation of their spectral envelopes. The phase of the noise spectra are randomized before the re-synthesis using standard phase vocoder.

However, the sinusoids and noise model represents the input signal as a sum of slowly-varying sinusoids and noise, and it is not able to preserve the quality of transients. Thus, the model was extended with a separate transient modeling resulting in the sinusoids, transients and noise model [Verma and Meng, 1998a], [Verma and Meng, 2000]. In these approaches, the transients are extracted from the input signal before applying the sinusoidal and noise model on it. During TS, the individual transients are only shifted in time according to the desired TS factor without any further modification. TS is achieved by modifying the rate at which the sinusoidal and noise parameters evolve over time [Verma and Meng, 1998b].

Partial Phase Derivative The standard PV phase propagation does not take into account the partial phase derivative in the frequency direction. A technique in which phase propagation is based on the full phase gradient estimated during the analysis stage has been proposed [Prusa and Holighaus, 2017]. During the synthesis, the phase is propagated using the real-time phase gradient heap integration algorithm [Prusa and Søndergaard, 2016] which is able to take into account the partial phase derivative in the frequency direction. It was shown that this technique is able to preserve the quality of the transients during modification, without explicit handling of transients.

Multi-Resolution An adaptive multi-resolution TS technique based on the PV has been proposed [Juillerat and Hirsbrunner, 2017]. Only the magnitude is processed with multiple, adaptive time-frequency resolutions, whereas the phase is processed using a unique resolution to preserve the phase coherence between the different resolutions components. This is done by first processing both the phase and magnitude using a single resolution phase vocoder with scaled phase locking.

Then the magnitude is fixed through the multiple resolutions magnitude correction step.

A separation based on the signal transience [Juillerat et al., 2008] is applied to the signal, and higher time resolution is used for transients whereas higher frequency resolution is used for steady sounds. Three degree of transience are proposed, allowing the weak and strong transience components to be processed with different resolutions.

2.3 Harmonic/Percussive Source Separation

Harmonic/Percussive separation (HPS) goal is to separate pitched (harmonic) instruments from percussion instruments.

Most HPS algorithms are based on the intuition that harmonic instruments form stable horizontal ridges across time in the spectrograms, whereas percussive instruments form stable vertical ridges across frequency due to their broadband noise-based nature. A spectrogram containing harmonic and percussive elements is shown in Fig. 6. However, there are sound whose nature is not clearly harmonic neither percussive such as white noise or applause.

Some HPS scenarios are introduced and the outcomes of an ideal HPS are proposed. The first scenario is inspired from Fig. 6. There are two instruments, the first with harmonic nature whereas the second with percussive nature. The ideal separation would assign all the former to the harmonic component, and all the latter to the percussive component. Let us think instead about the sound of a note played on the piano. Initially, when the hammer hits the string, the sound has a percussive nature. Later, when the string is vibrating, the sound shows a harmonic nature. Ideally, the first part of the sound should be assigned to the percussive component whereas the second part to the harmonic one. On the other side, human singing has a peculiar behavior when processed by this separation. This is mainly because the sound of a human voice does not show a clear harmonic nature neither a percussive one. Therefore, slices of time/frequency regions are almost randomly assigned to both the harmonic and the percussive components. In addition, singers often apply

Figure 6: Spectrogram illustrating ideal harmonic and percussive components. Each horizontal ridge identifies an element of the harmonic component, whereas each vertical ridge identifies one element of the percussive one. The image has been adapted from [Fitzgerald, 2010].

vibrato which breaks the assumption that the elements of the harmonic component can be modeled as perfectly horizontal ridges in the spectrogram.

2.3.1 Harmonic/Percussive Separation using Median Filtering

The HPS method based on median filtering [Fitzgerald, 2010] used the observation that, given a magnitude spectrogram X , the elements of the harmonic components form ridges on the frequency axis (horizontally), whereas the elements of the transient components form ridges on the time axis (vertically). Fig. 7 illustrates the intermediate results of each step of the procedure.

The median filtering is effective for this task because it can be used to suppress outliers in a one-dimensional series while enhancing patterns. With the application of a

Figure 7: Overview of the intermediate outputs of each step of the Harmonic/Percussive separation using Median Filtering procedure. (a): Magnitude spectrogram X . (b): Horizontally and vertically median-filtered magnitude spectrograms, also named enhanced enhanced spectrograms. The harmonic one \tilde{Y}_h is on the left, whereas the percussive \tilde{Y}_p is on the right. (c): Binary masks. The harmonic mask M_h is on the left, whereas the percussive M_p is on the right. (d): Masked spectrograms. The harmonic X_h is on the left, whereas the percussive X_p is on the right. The image has been adapted from [Driedger et al., 2014].

median filter through the time axis (horizontally) is possible to obtain the harmonic enhanced spectrogram \tilde{Y}_h where the horizontal ridges are enhanced and the vertical ridges are suppressed. The application of a median filtering through the frequency axis generates instead the percussive enhanced spectrogram \tilde{Y}_p , where the effect on

horizontal and vertical ridges is inverted.

The information of the two enhanced spectrograms is combined to generate the harmonic (M_h) and percussive (M_p) masks. The masks can either be binary or fuzzy, depending on how each time-frequency bin is associated to the masks generated. In binary masking, each time-frequency bin is completely assigned to only one mask, whereas in fuzzy masking each time-frequency bin is loosely assigned to both masks. The magnitude spectrograms of the harmonic (X_h) and the percussive (X_p) components are obtained by Wiener filtering of the original spectrogram with the harmonic and the percussive masks.

2.3.2 Harmonic/Percussive Separation using Kernel Additive Modelling

Kernel Additive Modelling (KAM) is a framework for sound source separation [Liutkus et al., 2014b], [Liutkus et al., 2014a]. It assumes that a source at some location can be estimated using its values at nearby locations. The nearness is defined through a source specific proximity kernel. This process has analogies with the human perception. As pointed out by Auditory Scene Analysis, humans tend to use local features such as repeativity, common fate and continuity to discriminate between sources in a mixture. Different sources are modelled using different kernels and the iterative kernel backfitting algorithm is used to separate them.

The KAM framework has been proposed to generalise, extend and improve the HPS using Median Filtering [Rafii et al., 2014]. Namely, through KAM, the separation can be refined through several iterations and multi-channel mixtures can be accounted.

The HPS algorithm based on Median Filtering can be viewed as a single instance of KAM. In order to implement the Median Filtering approach within the KAM framework is enough to define the proximity kernel of the percussive source equal to the median filter used through the vertical dimension, and define the proximity kernel for the harmonic source equal to the median filter used through the horizontal dimension. The comparison between the HPS based on median filtering and the

HPS based on KAM carried out in the original paper [Rafii et al., 2014] has been done using the PEASS toolkit [Emiya et al., 2011]. This toolkit contains objective perceptive metrics to evaluate sound separation. It turned out that a low number of KAM iterations has shown significant improvements in the average of the Overall Perceptual Score(OPS) over the median filtering algorithm. However, the validity of these results is questionable because a study on objective measures for HPS shows that there is no strong correlation between the PEASS ratings and the results obtained via listening tests [Cano et al., 2016]. This study suggested that PEASS metrics do not generalize well to tasks outside those used in training PEASS, including HPS.

Whereas it is likely that KAM improves the perceptual quality of HPS based on median filtering, this improvement cannot be taken as granted only by looking at the PEASS metrics.

2.4 Time-Stretching technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation

A TS technique based on HPS has been proposed in literature [Driedger et al., 2014]. This technique addressed the TS transient issue from a new perspective. The authors claimed that, in order to preserve transients, there is no need to apply explicit transient detection in time. In addition, the authors stated that TS might benefit from avoiding explicit transient detection in time: errors in the detection directly affect the output of the transformation and a perceptual transparent preservation of transients, even when they are correctly detected, is not trivial.

The technique is based on the separation of a signal into the harmonic and percussive components and on the utilization of standard TS techniques, taking advantage of the characteristic of each component. The PV is applied to the harmonic component because it is suitable to process polyphonic stationary signals. On the other hand, the Standard Overlap-Add (OLA) is used to process the percussive component which ideally contains transients. The authors claimed that OLA is able to preserve transients if applied using a short frame size and a short hop size. Intuitively, the

Figure 8: Overview of the Time-Stretching technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation. (a): Input recording x . (b): Separation in harmonic x_h and percussive x_p components. (c): Time-Stretching on the single components. The phase vocoder is applied to the harmonic component, whereas OLA is applied to the percussive one. (d): The time-stretched components obtained from (c) are superposed. The image has been adapted from [Driedger et al., 2014].

introduction of phase jumps does not influence the chaotic nature of phases of noise-like signals and the short frame and hop sizes reduce the stuttering effect making it not perceivable. Finally, the individual time-stretched components are superposed to obtain the final output. Fig. 8 illustrates the approach used by the TS technique based on HPSs.

The technique showed to perform better on highly percussive signals and on complex mixtures, whereas it showed to perform worse when applied to a monophonic synthesized track or to a singing voice recording. The authors justified the first observation with the ability of their technique to keep the transients crisp while preserving the harmonic component around these transients. The issue with the monophonic synthesized track seemed to be related to the phasiness artefact, whereas the singing voice one has been linked to the bad performance of HPS applied to human speech.

In this case, a relevant fraction of the signal which should be assigned to the harmonic component was instead assigned to the percussive component. This broke the assumption that the percussive component is noise-like. As result, jump artefacts become too strong to be masked by the modified harmonic component.

Another TS technique based on HPS was proposed in 2017 [Damskäg and Välimäki, 2017], but we will make reference only to the one proposed in 2014 [Driedger et al., 2014].

2.5 Discussion

The TS technique based on HPS showed to be interesting for its ability to preserve naturally both the harmonic and the percussive elements. This is made particularly intriguing by its straightforward formulation. Despite the promising starting point, the technique could be improved. Namely, the technique might suffer from all the artefacts registered in time-segment processing and in time-frequency processing.

The time-segment processing artefacts that need to be considered are transient duplication, transient skipping and pitch distortion. Transient duplication and transient skipping should be avoided by setting short hop size and short frame size in overlap-add. Unless a significant leaking of the harmonic elements into the percussive component is registered, the pitch distortion should also be avoided.

On the other side, the time-frequency processing artefacts that need to be considered are: transient smearing, phasiness and timbre distortion. Unless a significant leaking of the percussive elements into the harmonic component is registered, transient smearing should be avoided. Phasiness is treated with identity phase locking. However, the phase coherence might be lost for sinusoids who change center frequency bin in successive frames. The technique might benefit from an occasional application of phase resets to recover the horizontal phase coherence for sinusoids as this might be lost. The timbre distortion is not treated in any way, therefore it is quite likely to be registered. Still, timbre distortion has shown to be negligible for some kind of the signal as it is not perceived. In addition, the technique does not provide stereo image preservation.

In the remainder of the chapter solution to improve the TS technique based on HPS

are proposed.

2.5.1 Harmonic/Percussive Separation

The technique might be honed by improving the separation. The leaking artefact and different type of separation might be explored. It is also interesting to get to know how (and to which extent) the improvements in the separation are reflected into the TS audio quality.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation Method The HPS method based on median filtering returns reasonable satisfying components. However, the leaking between the harmonic and the percussive components might be reduced. The HPS method based on KAM can be implemented in the TS technique based on HPS instead of the HPS method based on median filtering, as the former was proposed as improvement of the latter.

Separation Method Different type of separation can be tried as pre-processing step of the TS technique based on HPS instead of using the HPS. An example might be the separation based on the signal transience [Juillerat et al., 2008].

Multi-Resolution Harmonic/Percussive Separation Assuming that the recognition of the harmonic component is advantaged from a higher frequency resolution whereas the recognition of percussive one is advantaged from an higher time resolution, giving a multi-resolution spectrogram to a HPS technique might lead to an improvement.

Post-Processing on the Harmonic and Percussive Components Considering that the percussive component should contain only elements such as transients, all the elements that does not resemble a transient can be removed from the percussive component and can be given to the harmonic component. On the other side, elements of the harmonic component which resemble transients can be removed from the harmonic component and can be given to the percussive component.

Improving the Separation on Human Speech HPS cannot handle effectively the characteristics of human voices. A solution might consist in the extraction of speech signals as a separate component. However, it could also be interesting to study whether increasing the ability to recognize vibrato patterns for the harmonic component leads to an improvement.

2.5.2 Time-Stretching

Different TS methods can be proposed instead of the PV with identity phase locking and the standard overlap-add.

Transient Preservation and Percussive Component

- **Substitution of Overlap-Add:** The effectiveness of OLA in treating the percussive component could be explored more. A comparison of the transient preservation allowed by OLA and other transient preservation techniques might be carried out. Whereas the simplicity of the OLA is likely to be unbeatable, there may be methods that allow a better transient preservation. Especially considering extreme TS factors.
- **Transient Detection:** A total different approach consist in the use the percussive component for explicit transient detection. This may ease the transient detection process.

Phase Vocoder and Harmonic Component

- **Reduce Phasiness:** The scaled phase locking scheme has been shown to reduce/eliminate the phasiness of the identity phase locking scheme. Both schemes were proposed in the same paper [Laroche and Dolson, 1999]. However, the scaled phase locking scheme was suggested as improvement of the identity phase locking scheme. The scaled phase locking can correctly follow sinusoids whose center frequency bin change over time.
- **Allow Timbre Preservation:** Waveform preservation extension can be explored.

- Multi-Resolution PV: Multi-resolution processing might reduce the impact of percussive elements leaked into the harmonic component.

Adaptive Multi-Resolution Phase Vocoder based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation HPS might be used as pre-processing step in the adaptive multi-resolutional phase vocoder [Juillerat and Hirsbrunner, 2017] instead of the separation method based on the signal transience.

During the remainder of the thesis only the first point will be considered. The HPS based on KAM will be tested inside the TS technique based on HPS.

Chapter 3

Proposed Technique and Evaluation

3.1 Proposed Technique

The improved technique inherited the use of the phase vocoder and of the overlap-add to time-stretch the harmonic and the percussive components from the original Time-Stretching technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation [Driedger et al., 2014] (TS-HPS). However, the Harmonic/Percussive Separation algorithm based on Median Filtering [Fitzgerald, 2010] (HPS-MED) has been substituted with the algorithm based on Kernel Additive Models [Rafii et al., 2014] (HPS-KAM). HPS-MED and HPS-KAM can be exchanged transparently without the modification of anything else in the original TS-HPS system. The only difference was that HPS-KAM required an additional parameter for the number of iterations. Fig. 9 shows the block diagrams of the original technique and of the improved technique.

3.1.1 Parameters Proposed

The quality of the outcome of the system depends on the parameters used. Most of the critical parameters involved are inherited from the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) model. Two STFTs are computed. The first one is applied by the HPS. The time-domain representation of the harmonic component obtained from the HPS is then given to a second STFT computed by the phase vocoder. Finally, the time-

Figure 9: Block diagrams of the original technique and of the improved technique. The only difference is the method used to extract the harmonic and percussive components. (a) Uses the Harmonic/Percussive separation based on Median Filtering. (b) Uses the Harmonic/Percussive separation based on Kernel Additive Model.

domain representation obtained is sum to the time-stretched percussive component to generate the output.

Sample Rate We considered a sample rate of 44100 Hz using a sample period of 0.023 ms. Notice that most parameters need to be adjusted for sample rates. The effectiveness of most parameters depends on the time range they cover rather than the amount of samples they process.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation using Kernel Additive Models The HPS used 4096 samples of the original signal to create the frames for the STFT. A same length Hamming window weighted each frame before the application of the Fast Fourier Transform. The time length of a frame was 93 ms, whereas the bin frequency range was 11 Hz. The hop size was 1024 samples, meaning that the distance between consecutive frames was 23 ms. Binary masking was used to get the masks. The median filters applied to get the harmonic enhanced spectrogram and the percussive enhanced spectrograms were both 17 bins long. A range of 187 Hz is covered from the median filter applied on the frequency direction, whereas a period of 391 ms is covered from the median filter applied on the time direction. These median filter lengths were taken from the publication proposing the HPS-MED [Fitzgerald, 2010].

However, there was no evidence that this was the best parameters combination. For instance, a recent TS approach based on soft masking proposed different bin lengths for the two median filters [Damskäg and Välimäki, 2017].

The only parameter introduced by HPS-KAM to HPS-MED is the number of iteration carried out to compute the components. Considering that the mathematical convergence of the algorithm had shown to be not related to a perceptual improvement of the separation, we could not assume that more iterations led to better results. We decided to use 2 iteration. This seemed to be an acceptable value based on the evaluation results stated in the original paper [Rafi et al., 2014]. However, even in this case there was no evidence that this was the best value available. In addition, an optimal value showed to be signal-dependent.

Phase Vocoder The Phase Vocoder used 2048 samples to create each frame. A Hanning window of the same sized was applied on it before applying the Fast Fourier Transform. Each frame has duration of 46 ms. The synthesis hop size used by the inverse-STFT was fixed at 512 samples. The analysis hop size is instead obtained considering the TS factor and the synthesis hop size. The identity phase locking scheme was applied [Laroche and Dolson, 1999].

Overlap-Add Overlap-Add used a frame size of 256 samples with duration of 6 ms. A hanning window of the same size was applied. The synthesis hop size was fixed at 128 sample with duration of 3 ms. The analysis hop size is obtained starting from the stretching factor and the synthesis hop size as for the phase vocoder.

3.2 Evaluation

To check whether the modification of the HPS method of the TS-HPS led to an improvement, we carried out a listening test. Before choosing for a listening test we considered alternatives to evaluate the improvement. However, we have not found any objective measure suitable for the evaluation of Time-Stretching (TS). Even though objective perceptual measures are available for coding [Thiede et al., 2000] or for separation [Emiya et al., 2011], they are decisively not appropriate for TS. In

fact, we observed listening tests are usually proposed to evaluate TS.

A recent publication used a listening test to get the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) to compare the quality of TS [Driedger et al., 2014]. The subjects were asked to rate the audio quality of the outcome of different TS methods applied on a set of stimuli using a scale from 1 (bad) to 5 (excellent). Then, the results were averaged respect to the subjects obtaining the MOS. A further average respect to the stimuli gave a summary measure for each TS method, with which they can be compared. However, we needed a different test, as the goal of our evaluation was different. We wanted to check whether the modification of the method used for HPS was linked to an improvement in the outcome of the TS, and not only compare the quality of the outcome of the TS.

3.2.1 The Listening Test

The listening test was prepared using the Web Audio Evaluation Tool (WEAT) [Jillings et al., 2015], [Jillings et al., 2016] and conducted online. The listeners were asked to use headphones and to carry out two tasks. In the first task the listeners were asked to vote for the HPS modification they preferred. Instead, in the second task they were asked to vote for the TS modification they preferred. In both tasks three stimuli were presented using an AB interface built using WEAT. One of the three stimuli was the original sample unprocessed, whereas the other two were the transformations obtained using the evaluated methods. The listeners were aware of the presence of the original sample as they were told about its presence. They could also visually recognize it: the look of its box was different from the remaining two boxes. The order in which the stimuli were presented in each trial was random, and also the order of the pages containing the stimuli was randomized. The same original stimuli has been used to develop both tasks.

3.2.2 Task 1: Time-Stretching Evaluation

The interface used for Time-Stretching Evaluation is showed in Fig.10. In the first task of test the subjects were asked to answer to the question:

Figure 10: Screenshot of the interface used for Time-Stretching Evaluation.

“ Which version does sound better? If no one does, select “they sound the same”. ”.

The task was specified as:

“ If you can hear a difference in the amount of audio quality degradation between the versions, you should indicate as better the one showing less. ”

The independent variables considered were:

- 6 Stimuli: Discussed later
- 2 Time-Stretching Techniques:
 1. Time-Stretching Technique using Harmonic/Percussive Separation based on Median Filtering
 2. Time-Stretching Technique using Harmonic/Percussive Separation based on Kernel Additive Model
- 2 Time-Stretching Factors:
 1. 0.8
 2. 1.2

The choice of the Time-Stretching factors to be considered was not trivial. We considered a reasonable range of utilization between 0.5 (doubling the speed) and

2.0 (slowing three times the speed). Initially, we wanted to test using TS factors of 0.5, 0.8, 1.2 and 2. In the literature a listening test proposed the TS factors 0.5, 0.8, 1.2, 1.8 and 3 instead [Driedger et al., 2014]. However, we decided to focus only on two TS factors because we wanted that the two tasks of the listening test to be carried out in less than 20 minutes. We also wanted both contraction and expansion to be evaluated, leading us to the choice of 0.8 and 1.2 as TS factors.

3.2.3 Task 2: Harmonic/Percussive Separation Evaluation

The interface used for Harmonic/Percussive Separation Evaluation is showed in Fig.11. In the second task of test the subjects were asked to answer to one between

Figure 11: Screenshot of the interface used for Harmonic/Percussive Separation Evaluation.

two versions of the question. The version shown on each page depended on the component presented in it:

“ Which version of the HARMONIC component does sound more natural and free of percussive sounds? If no one does, select “they sound the same”. ” and

“ Which version of the PERCUSSIVE component does sound more natural and free of harmonic sounds? If no one does, select “they sound the same”. ”. In this case, the task was specified as:

“ A component is considered natural if the sources assigned to it are chosen correctly and if it sounds like they have been recorded separately. ”.

The independent variables considered were:

- 6 Stimuli: Discussed later
- 2 Harmonic/Percussive separation methods:
 1. Harmonic/Percussive Separation based on Median Filtering
 2. Harmonic/Percussive Separation based on Kernel Additive Model
- 2 Target Components (or Sources):
 1. Harmonic
 2. Percussive

3.2.4 Stimuli

The set of stimuli was made of six audio signals. Four were taken from a previous publication [Driedger et al., 2014]. The other two were extracted from professional audio recordings. Even though the set covers a wide range of signals, it was not supposed to cover statistically the whole range on which a TS technique can be applied to, and therefore was not appropriate for a quantitative comparison between the two methods. However, considering the qualitative and exploratory approach of our research, the test showed to create sufficient data to support a discussion.

The stimuli were:

1. “CastanetViolin”: Simple mixture containing the percussive sound of the castanet and the harmonic sound of the violin.
2. “Jazz”: Synthetic polyphonic sound mixture of a trumpet, a piano, a bass and drums.
3. “Sweet Home Alabama” excerpt from “Sweet Home Alabama” by Lynyrd Skynyrd.
4. “Rio”: excerpt from “Rio” by Netsky.
5. “PolySynth”: Sound mixture of several polyphonic synthesizers.

6. “SingingVoice”: Solo male singing voice.

NB: The first two and the last two stimuli needed to be up-sampled from 22050 Hz to 44100 Hz to be processed with the Harmonic/Percussive Separation based on Kernel Additive Model. This operation was carried out using the Sound eXchange (Sox) tool. The up-sampling degrades slightly the audio quality. This was audible on the CastanetViolin example. However, this had not affected the evaluation.

3.2.5 Subjects

32 subjects took part in the test. Most of them claimed to have expertise as technical listeners, defined as having at least 3 years of experience in areas concerning research in the field of audio, music production, or development of audio software/hardware. Namely, only two of them claimed to be not experts.

Fake test pages were presented to the listeners in order to check whether they understood correctly the tasks and could recognize whether there was no difference between the audio examples proposed. In each fake page, the two examples compared contained the same audio signals. Therefore, the listeners were expected to vote for “they sound the same”. We decided to not consider the answers of listeners who were not able to recognize correctly at least half fake tests. 4 subjects did not pass the criteria, thus were not considered in the evaluation.

For a bug in the system, it was possible to submit pages without giving an answer. That is the reason why we could not collect some results and some pages showed a different amount of answers.

3.3 Results of the Evaluation

The results of the listening test are presented in Fig. 12. A thorough discussion of the listening test is available in the appendix. In addition, the appendix contains a description of the audio signals and of the artefacts detected in the transformed signals. In this section the results are summarized.

First, we can notice that the difference of the results between the TSM slower (TS

	HPS Harmonic			HPS Percussive			TSM Slower			TSM Faster		
	KAM	MED	SAM	KAM	MED	SAM	KAM	MED	SAM	KAM	MED	SAM
CastanetViolin	24	1	3	16	7	4	5	6	13	3	6	16
Jazz	17	4	6	25	1	1	13	9	2	11	7	6
Sweet Home Al.	21	5	1	24	2	1	16	1	7	16	3	6
Rio	23	2	2	27	0	1	20	5	1	14	5	6
PolySynth	7	11	8	17	8	2	10	7	7	8	9	10
SingingVoice	7	10	10	15	7	5	1	24	0	0	23	1

Figure 12: Heatmap summarizing the results of the listening test. Each row represent a stimulus, whereas each columns represent a answer that could have been given by the listeners. The columns are grouped by task. For each task, there are 3 possible answers: Kernel Additive Model (KAM), Median Filtering (MED) and They Sound The Same (SAM). Each different answer is characterized by a different color: green for KAM, red for MED and light blue for SAM.

factor 1.2) and TSM faster (TS factor 0.8) tasks is small. Therefore, we will focus only on the results of the the TSM slower task. Still, it can be noticed that the KAM versions of the TSM Faster task registered slightly less votes respect to the TSM slower task.

Second, we can notice that the KAM versions of the percussive component has been always preferred to the MED versions. A similar pattern can be retrieved for the HPS Harmonic task, excluding the PolySynth and SingingVoice stimuli, for which no relevant difference between the answers has been registered. Therefore, a tangible improvement in the HPS has been recorded only for the first four stimuli: CastanetViolin, Jazz, Sweet Home Alabama and Rio. We can now move to the results of the TS and look for relationships between the improvement in the HPS and the results of the TS.

Two trends emerged from this subset of 4 stimuli. Whereas for the CastanetViolin stimulus no improvement was registered for TS, an improvement was recorded for the remaining three stimuli. Considering the audio characteristics of the stimuli this suggested that an improvement is recorded for complex mixtures containing both harmonic and percussive elements.

Is interesting to notice that the SingingVoice stimulus did not contain a clear harmonic/percussive structure, therefore the application of HPS did not result in valid

components, especially for the percussive one. Apparently, the application of KAM worsen the outcome of the TS.

Finally, we can comment about the artefacts that might be detected using the Time-Stretching Technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation. No relevant artefacts are registered whether the components obtained with the HPS contained a negligible amount of residual of the other component. However, if the percussive component contains substantial amount of harmonic residual the pitch distortion artefact, typical of the overlap-add, is audible. The percussive residual in the harmonic component might instead lead to the transient smearing artefact, typical of the phase vocoder.

Chapter 4

Final Discussion

In these chapter we briefly review the results obtained from the listening test and the analysis of the audio files and advise where to look for further improvements. In the first section, the issues related to harmonic/percussive separation (HPS) are discussed. The improvements achieved and the limitations encountered are clarified. In the second section, the time stretching (TS) is treated. The drawback found out are discussed and method to overstep them are proposed.

4.1 Harmonic/Percussive Separation

If the signal processed contains a clear harmonic/percussive structure, the Kernel Additive Model version of HPS improves the Median Filtering version, as shown from the cases of the mixtures CastanetViolin, Jazz, Sweet Home Alabama and Rio. Actually, the improvement seemed to be bigger for complex mixtures like real recordings. In the case of PolySynth was not clear whether the introduction of the KAM introduced an enhancement, whereas its introduction for SingingVoice worsened the separation. As discussed more than once in the thesis, the definition of Harmonic/Percussive components we gave was not applicable to speech signals. In addition, we found pretty interesting the fact that the hi-hats were usually assigned to the harmonic component. Probably, like crashes, hi-hats have a relevant extension in both time and frequency axis of the spectrogram, breaking the assumption

that percussive elements are vertical ridges.

Still, the results shown to be distant from what we described as the ideal separation. Different amounts of leaking of the elements of one component into the other component was always registered. This amount showed to be relevant, as it makes the difference from TS artefacts which can or cannot be covered from the final superposition.

4.2 Time-Stretching

Let us consider only the stimuli for which the application of KAM resulted in a tangible improvement. The separation of the simple mixture CastanetViolins has been improved, but this has not been reflected in the Time-Stretching. The reason may lie behind the presence of the smearing of entire notes in the KAM version of the percussive component. This smearing seemed to be not relevant during the evaluation of the HPS. However, this artefact had been amplified by the application of TS resulting in the pitch distortion artefact.

On the other side, complex mixtures (Jazz, Sweet Home Alabama and Rio) showed to reflect a significant improvement from the HPS to the TS. However, these complex mixtures also gave an insight of the weaknesses of the Time-Stretching Technique based on Harmonic/Percussive Separation. The TS outcome strictly relies on the quality of the separation. The harmonic elements leaked in the percussive component are treated with overlap-add causing the pitch distortion artefact. On the other side, the percussive elements leaked into the harmonic component are treated with the phase vocoder causing the transient smearing. Whether the separation is optimal or sub-optimal these artefacts are negligible, but for most complex mixtures this is not likely to be the case. However, modification of the technique used by the time-stretching could reduce the dependence from the HPS quality. Namely, the technique could benefit from moving towards a multi-resolution phase vocoder similar to one proposed in literature [Juillerat and Hirsbrunner, 2017]. Other interesting tricks can be implemented to further improve. More than one multi-resolucional method can be simultaneously used [Juillerat and Hirsbrunner, 2017] and stereo preservation can be

introduced [Bonada, 2000]. Finally, against the main reason why the TS technique using HPS was originally proposed, an explicit transient detection and processing can be carried out [Röbel, 2003] taking advantage of the observation that transients are supposed to be only assigned to the percussive component.

Appendices

Appendix A

First Appendix: Listening Test

In this appendix a detailed analysis of the results of the listening is presented. The answers of the listening test for each stimuli are shown using histograms. In addition, spectrograms showing the original stimuli and the harmonic and percussive components obtained using the two different methods are shown.

Given a stimulus, the results of the listening test are summarized in four histograms. Each one contains the result of a single tasks:

1. Harmonic Separation: Harmonic component obtained from the Harmonic/Percussive Separation (HPS).
2. Percussive separation: Percussive component obtained from the Harmonic/Percussive Separation (HPS).
3. Expansion: Time-Stretching (TS) using factor 1.2.
4. Contraction: Time-Stretching (TS) using factor 0.8.

Every histogram shows three bars. These are used to quantify the amount of subjects who voted for each answer. Namely, the bars represent:

1. Kernel Additive Model: amount of subjects who preferred the Kernel Additive Model (KAM) version.

2. Median Filtering: amount of subjects who preferred the Median Filtering (MED) version.
3. No preference: amount of subjects who claimed that they did not prefer any version.

A.1 Castanet Violin

The Castanet Violin stimulus is the simplest mixture in the set. As its name suggest, it contains the sound the harmonic sound of a violin and the percussive sound of a castanet. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 13, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 14.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

As conveyed from the first two histograms in Fig. 14, most subjects preferred the KAM versions for the HPS of both components. Especially regarding the separation of the harmonic component, the preference for the KAM version was almost unanimous. This is uphold by Fig. 15, where it can be observed that the leaking of percussive residual into the KAM Version is significantly lower.

Less listeners preferred the KAM version for the Percussive component. Even though the KAM version contains globally less harmonic residual leaking, a pair of notes that were supposed to be assigned to the harmonic component are instead assigned to the percussive component. This is shown and discussed in Fig. 16.

Time-Stretching

More than half subjects claimed that they did not perceive any difference in the outcome of Time-Stretching. We can get an interesting observation by listening to the time-stretched versions of the single components (never proposed in the listening test). The time-stretched KAM version of the percussive component shows an annoying artefact in the time location where the full notes were leaked. The degradation is ascribable to the pitch distortion artefact raised from the application of overlap-add on harmonic signal without preserving the horizontal phase coherence.

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 13: Spectrograms for CastanetViolin. The first has been computed using a frame size of 1024 samples, whereas for the second one a frame size of 8092 is used. In the first spectrogram the frequency axis is linear, whereas in the second one this is logarithmic and covers a wider range of frequencies. The horizontal ridges are caused by the sound of the violin. In the first spectrogram a vibrato effect can be recognized, whereas in the second one it can be seen that at 2 and at 6 seconds two notes are played simultaneously. On the other side, the vertical ridges are caused by the sound of the castanet.

Results for the first stimulus: CastanetViolin

Figure 14: Histograms showing the listening test results for the CastanetViolin stimulus. The first two histograms show that most subjects preferred the KAM version for both the Harmonic and the Percussive components. From the last two histograms it can be seen that more than half subjects claimed that they did not perceive any difference in the outcome of TS for either Expansion and Contraction.

CastanetViolin Harmonic Component Spectrograms

(a) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 15: Harmonic Component Spectrograms for the CastanetViolin stimulus. The leaking of percussive elements in the harmonic component is dramatically decreased in the KAM version. For instance, the vertical ridges at half and at 1 second in the MED version are almost vanished in the KAM version.

CastanetViolin Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 16: Percussive Component Spectrograms for the CastanetViolin stimulus. The leaking of the harmonic elements is higher in the MED version. However, in the KAM version a pair of notes (horizontal ridges) are registered at 1.5 and at 5.5 seconds in the low frequencies. The MED version does not show these notes. The origin of this leaking and the reason why is recorded only in the KAM version is unclear.

This artefact showed to be not negligible after the two time-stretched components are superposed.

Discussion

Apparently, the subjects perceived an improvement in the KAM version of HPS, whereas the two versions of TS were perceived as comparable.

However, from this example an important insight about the weakness of the TS technique based on HPS has emerged. Whether the outcome of HPS in most cases is acceptable, the leaking of the elements that should be given to one component into the other component might lead to audible artefacts.

A.2 Jazz

The Jazz stimulus contains a synthetic polyphonic mixture of trumpet, piano, bass and drums. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 17, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 18.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

The listeners preferred the KAM version of HPS for both components. The hi-hat tends to be wrongly assigned to the harmonic component in both versions. The presence of the hi-hat is stronger in the MED version, but in the KAM version sounds less natural. Whereas the KAM version of the harmonic component tends to sound cleaner, it seems it has a light low-pass filter applied on it. Still, the listeners tend to prefer the KAM version of the harmonic component, but showing less margin than the one showed for the percussive component.

Fig. 20 shows the two versions of the percussive component. It is evident that KAM improved the MED, as confirmed by the results of the listening test.

Time-Stretching

As observed from the previous stimulus, the leaking of harmonic elements in the percussive component leads to audible TS artefacts. The leaking of the harmonic

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 17: Spectrogram for the Jazz stimulus. From the spectrograms, it can be seen that this is a thick mixture, containing both harmonic and both percussive components.

Results for the second stimulus: Jazz

Figure 18: Histograms showing the listening test results for the Jazz stimulus. From the first two histograms it can be seen that the subjects showed preference for the KAM version of HPS. Whereas for the harmonic component half listeners indicated the KAM version as better, the preference was almost unanimous for the percussive component.

From the last two histograms it can be seen that the KAM version of the TS was preferred. However, the difference between the KAM and HPS version was smaller for the TS task.

Jazz Harmonic Component Spectrograms

(a) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 19: Harmonic Component Spectrograms for the Jazz stimulus. The two versions look comparable. Both contain vertical patterns which can be attributed to the hi-hat.

Jazz Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 20: Percussive Component Spectrograms for the Jazz stimulus. The KAM version of the percussive component contains less harmonic residual leaking. Especially in the frequency range between 100 Hz and 1000 Hz. This upholds the results of the listening test, which showed that almost all listeners chose the KAM version.

elements into the percussive component leads to the overlap-add pitch distortion artefact. A not negligible amount of subjects preferred the KAM version as better, but still a significant amount showed preference for the Median Filtering version.

Discussion

The listeners tended to prefer the KAM version of HPS. Differently from the previous stimulus, most subjects claimed to perceive a difference in the two versions of TS showing to prefer the KAM version.

The observation seemed to suggest that the margin of improvement of HPS tends to be bigger for more complex mixtures. Then, this improvement is reflected more into TS.

A.3 Sweet Home Alabama

The Sweet Home Alabama stimulus contains an extract of a professional rock recording with guitars, bass and drums. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 21, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 22.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

The HPS achieved on real recording is distant from the ideal one. Actually, the improvement of the KAM version is impressive in this case, especially for the percussive component as upheld by the results of the listening test.

Time-Stretching

The improvement introduced by the KAM version of HPS was substantial. As result, most of the listener could hear an improvement in the KAM version of TS.

However, the artefacts discussed before emerged more clearly. The leaking of harmonic elements into the percussive component lead again to the pitch distortion artefact. In addition, the leaking of percussive elements into harmonic component leads to the phase vocoder transient smearing artefact.

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 21: Spectrograms for the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. The spectrograms contain both harmonic and percussive components, and its complexity is comparable to the Jazz stimulus.

Results for the third stimulus: Sweet Home Alabama

Figure 22: Histograms showing the listening test results for the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. From the first two histograms it can be seen that the KAM versions of both harmonic and percussive components are preferred from almost all the subjects. The same trend can be found for the TS task, in which more than half subjects showed their preference for the KAM version.

Sweet Home Alabama Harmonic Component Spectrograms

(a) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 23: Harmonic Component Spectrograms for the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. The presence of the vertical patterns implies the involvement of residual of percussive elements in both versions.

Sweet Home Alabama Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 24: Percussive Component Spectrograms for the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. Leaking from the harmonic elements into the percussive component is observed, as implied by the presence of horizontal patterns. However, the KAM version contains less harmonic residual in the range between 100Hz and 1000Hz.

We applied not extreme TS factors, and we expect that for higher values the registered artefacts become more prominent.

Discussion

The improvement obtained by the application of the KAM is substantial for either HPS and TS. However, shortcomings of not having perfect separated sources emerged. The TS approach might benefit from solutions that would make it more resistant to the leaking artefact of HPS.

A.4 Rio

The Rio audio signal contains an extract of a professional Drum'n'Bass recording. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 27, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 26.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

As for the case of Sweet Home Alabama the HPS improvement of the KAM is relevant, as supported by the results of the listening test and Figs. ??, 28. Still, the hi-hats tended to be wrongly assigned to the harmonic component and not to the percussive component.

Time-Stretching

The TS observation are comparable to the observation for the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. The leaking of the harmonic elements into the percussive component and the leaking of percussive elements in the harmonic component lead to artefacts that were not covered by the superposition of the two components. However, considering the relevant enhancement of the HPS using the KAM version the outcome of the TS modification is perceived as improved.

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 25: Spectrograms for the Rio stimulus. We can see that the first spectrogram is really thick. A lot of harmonic and percussive elements cover almost all frequencies. From the second spectrogram we can see that the lowest frequencies events are the one associated with more energy.

Results for the fourth stimulus: Rio

(a) Harmonic Separation

(b) Percussive Separation

(c) Expansion (Slowing Down)

(d) Contraction (Speeding Up)

Figure 26: Histograms showing the listening test results for the Rio stimulus. From the first two histograms we can see that almost all subjects gave their preference to the KAM version of HPS for both harmonic and percussive components. The subjects also showed to prefer the KAM version of TS.

Rio Harmonic Component Spectrograms

(a) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 27: Harmonic Component Spectrograms for the Rio stimulus. Leaking of the percussive elements into the harmonic component is registered for both versions. For example, both spectrograms show a percussive source repeated in time with frequency range from the minimum displayed to 100 Hz (probably the kick). It is interesting to notice that, whereas the MED version showed a percussive source component around 200 Hz this was not registered in the KAM version. In addition, the horizontal ridge between 100 Hz and 1000 Hz in the KAM version tended to be more continuous. This is positive, because this reflects the stationary nature of the harmonic elements.

Rio Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 28: Percussive Component Spectrograms for the Rio stimulus. The leaking of harmonic elements into the percussive component is stronger in the MED version, especially in the range between 100 Hz and 1000 Hz. In addition, the percussive elements that were registered around 200 Hz in the MED version of the harmonic component are assigned correctly only in the KAM version of the percussive component.

Conclusion

Comparable to the Sweet Home Alabama stimulus. Considering that the ideal HPS is not achieved yet, a way to reduce artefacts in TS due to the component leaking artefact might improve further.

A.4.1 PolySynth

The Polysynth stimulus is a mixture of polyphonic synthesizers. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 31, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 30

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

Despite the listeners tended to prefer the KAM version of the percussive component, the general quality of the HPS on the PolySynth stimulus is not satisfying. Both versions of the component showed a relevant amount of residual from the other component. The two versions of the harmonic component sound comparable, but the listeners showed a slight preference for the MED version.

Time-Stretching

As we saw from the previous stimuli, the leaking of harmonic elements into the percussive component affected the quality of the overlap-add.

A difference in the pitch of the time-stretched percussive component using factor 0.8 and 1.2 is heard. This is clearly a pitch distortion artefact.

Discussion

This quality of the TS for both version is not satisfactory. Even though the nature of the artefacts is the same of the previous stimuli, their presence here is more relevant. The reason why the HPS misbehave in this case might be investigated more.

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 29: Spectrograms for the PolySynth stimulus. We can observe that this is a mixture containing both percussive and harmonic elements.

Results for the fifth stimulus: PolySynth

Figure 30: Histograms showing the listening test results for the PolySynth stimulus. From the first histogram we can observe that there is a slight preference of the MED version of the Harmonic component, whereas the KAM version was preferred for the percussive component. From the last two histogram we can see that three bars has comparable preferences.

PolySynth Harmonic Component Spectrograms

(a) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Harmonic Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 31: Harmonic Component Spectrograms for the PolySynth stimulus. No clear difference is observed by looking at the two spectrograms.

PolySynth Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 32: Percussive Component Spectrograms for PolySynth. The version obtained with KAM seemed to contain less harmonic leaking.

A.5 SingingVoice

The SingingVoice stimulus contains a recording of a man singing ‘What have you doing? Let me be, stop messing with me’. Its spectrogram can be seen in Fig. 33, whereas the results of the listening test for it are shown in Fig. 34.

Harmonic/Percussive Separation

The two versions of the harmonic component were perceived comparable, whereas for the percussive components the KAM version was preferred. However, The listeners’ evaluation of the harmonic and percussive components was a difficult task as HPS showed to be not suitable for human speech signals. From an aural point of view, whether the two versions of a component might sound different, there is no way to tell which one better represent the harmonic or the percussive components.

Time-Stretching

The MED versions of TS were preferred unanimously. This is justified by the fact that the KAM version of the harmonic component sounds less natural than the MED version. The application of the phase vocoder on the former make it sounds even more unnatural. The presence of only harmonic elements in the percussive component led again to the pitch distortion artefact. For that case, the KAM version of time-stretched percussive component sounding slightly better when considered alone.

Discussion

As already observed in a previous publication [Driedger et al., 2014], the application of the TS technique using HPS on speech leads to poor results. The application of KAM even worsen the outcome. Probably this could be interpreted as an “improvement in the wrong direction”. As the first application of HPS by using MED did not show positive results, iterating it using KAM just moved us away from a good perceptual solution.

(a) Original Spectrogram

(b) Original Spectrogram (Higher Freq. Resolution)

Figure 33: Spectrograms for the SingingVoice stimulus. The spectrograms show the typical characteristics of speech signals. All the harmonics follow a monophonic fundamental pitch and the formants can be easily recognized. It shows a noisy pattern between 5 and 6 seconds, where a sibling 's' is sang. However, at the beginning of the 'd' sound of 'doing' (at 1 second at half) 'b' sound of 'be' (just before 4 seconds) the sound shows a slightly percussive nature.

Results for the sixth stimulus: SingingVoice

Figure 34: Histograms showing the listening test results for the SingingVoice stimulus. From the first histogram we can see that there was not clear preference between the two versions of the harmonic component, suggesting that they were comparable. On the other side, more than half subjects showed preference to the percussive component obtained using KAM.

Regarding TS, it turned out that the subjects preferred almost unanimously the MED version.

SingingVoice Percussive Component Spectrograms

(a) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Median Filtering)

(b) Percussive Component Spectrogram (Kernel Additive Model)

Figure 35: Percussive Component Spectrograms for the SingingVoice stimulus. The absence of vertical patterns for both spectrograms suggest that the nature of the signal represented is not percussive. As explained in Fig. 33 there is no clear percussive component in the spectrogram.

A.6 Final Remarks

The information obtained from the listening test was really relevant. This has been used to steer the navigation of the artefacts in the audio signals and upheld a reasonable discussion about it.

We can briefly comment the results by saying that generally the patterns emerging from the HPS task tends to be stronger than the one emerging from the TS task. This can be linked to the informal complaints of some subjects about the hardness in hearing differences during the TS task, especially when compared to the HPS task. This suggested that, if there is an improvement in TS linked to an improvement of the HPS, this must be slighter than the improvement of the HPS itself.

We can also comment about a problem emerged in the interpretation of the results when the answer was considered “statistically the same”. In these cases the answers of the subjects were equivalently divided into the three possible answers. The reading of these results is ambiguous. Does this mean that only some subjects were able to feel a slight difference, and this make them claim that one component was better than the other? We however decided to treat these cases as ‘statistically the same’, and propose that they were basically guessing. If we had asked to the listeners if they could hear a difference we could have obtained finer information about it. For instance, we could understand that the listeners heard a difference between the two versions, but neither of them sounds better than the other. In any case, these ambiguous situation were not in the spotlight of our research, as we were interested in tangible improvements between the two versions.

We decided to use two time-stretching factors, one for Expansion (1.2) and one for Contraction (0.8). From the results of the listening test this variable seems to be not significantly affecting the listeners’ preferences. However, we considered only not-extreme factors. Even though overlap-add showed to preserve decently the transients in this range, is almost sure that its behaviour worsen for more extreme factors. The transient will become evidently shorter or longer in these cases. In addition, we expect that the pitch distortion and transient smearing artefacts resulting from the leaking will be amplified by bigger factors.

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